

Environmental odor detection and classification with electronic nose system

Ricardo Macías-Quijas¹, Ramiro Velázquez¹, Carolina Del-Valle-Soto², Rafal Lizut³, Paolo Visconti⁴, Aimé Lay-Ekuakille⁴

¹Facultad de Ingeniería, Universidad Panamericana, Aguascalientes, Mexico

²Facultad de Ingeniería, Universidad Panamericana, Zapopan, Mexico

³Faculty of Natural and Technical Sciences, The John Paul II Catholic University of Lublin, Lublin, Poland

⁴Department of Innovation Engineering, University of Salento, Lecce, Italy

Article Info

Article history:

Received Jul 23, 2024

Revised Oct 22, 2024

Accepted Nov 19, 2024

Keywords:

Electronic nose

Filter diagonalization method

Odor recognition

Random forest

Spectral footprint

ABSTRACT

A prototype of an electronic nose (e-nose) system integrating a set of general-purpose gas sensors, an electronic module, and signal processing and classification methods has been designed and implemented to detect certain environmental odors that might pose a risk to human health. The proposed device explores the filter diagonalization method (FDM), an advanced signal processing technique for accurate spectral estimation, to detect the presence of odors together with random forest (RF), a popular machine learning algorithm, to classify the features of such spectra. Experimental results show that the proposed FDM-RF approach can recognize the targeted odors with an accuracy of 96.4%.

This is an open access article under the [CC BY-SA](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/) license.

Corresponding Author:

Ramiro Velázquez

Facultad de Ingeniería, Universidad Panamericana

Josemaría Escrivá de Balaguer 101, Aguascalientes, 20296, Mexico

Email: rvelazquez@up.edu.mx

1. INTRODUCTION

Mimicking human olfaction, which involves replicating the ability to detect and identify distinct odors, can be achieved using electronic noses (e-noses). E-noses encompass various sensors that detect and measure odors in their surroundings, each sensor responding differently to create unique patterns or “footprints” for each odor. Machine learning algorithms can then be trained on these footprints to recognize different odors.

E-noses have emerged as valuable instruments in various applications, from quality control in the food and wine industry to agriculture and environmental monitoring [1]-[3]. In particular, the scope of this technology in environmental monitoring is vast and fast-growing:

- Air quality assessment: E-noses have been used to track air quality, detecting harmful pollutants like carbon monoxide, nitrogen dioxide, and volatile organic compounds (VOCs), among others [4], [5]. They also assist in tracking pollution levels, providing pertinent data for urban air quality management [6].
- Water quality monitoring: E-noses can detect contaminants in water bodies by identifying odors associated with organic and chemical pollutants [7], [8].
- Industrial emissions control: E-noses can assist in detecting fugitive emissions and leakage points ensuring compliance with environmental policies and regulations [9], [10].

- d. Landfill monitoring: landfill sites emanate various odors that can be potentially pollutant and risky to human health. E-noses assist in detecting and monitoring these emissions, ensuring they remain within safe limits [11], [12].
- e. Disaster response: in the event of chemical spills or natural disasters, e-noses can provide rapid assessments of air and water quality, guiding emergency response efforts better and faster [13], [14].

This work overviews the design and prototyping of a novel e-nose system devoted to air quality monitoring that exhibits some interesting features such as low cost and high portability. The prototype is capable of detecting certain odors that might pose a threat to human well-being such as smoke, combustible gas, methane, alcohol, hydrogen, and several organic gases. Moreover, our work explores the filter diagonalization method (FDM), a powerful spectral estimation technique that obtains reliable footprints from the odor temporal signals, together with random forest (RF), a robust machine learning technique to classify such footprints and recognize odors accurately.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows: section 2 introduces the e-nose prototype, describes its associated methods (FDM and RF), and details the methodology used for the experimentation. Section 3 presents and discusses the findings of the study. Finally, section 4 concludes the paper by highlighting the main contributions and outlining perspectives for future work.

2. METHODS

2.1. Prototype

Figure 1(a) provides a system architecture overview of the proposed e-nose system. It encompasses seven different types of metal oxide semiconductor (MOS) sensors (S1-S7), a 32-bit microcontroller in charge of the sensors' signal acquisition and USB data transmission, and a computer, responsible for signal processing, classification, and data visualization. Figure 1(b) shows the prototype developed. It consists of a 3D-printed plastic case that hosts the set of sensors together with the electronic module and electrical connections. It is portable (mass: 500 g, dimensions: 6.5×5×7 cm) and low-cost (150 USD) [15]. Table 1 summarizes the target detection odors by each of the seven sensors in the device. Note that sensors react to a target odor but are also sensitive to secondary odors.

Figure 1. E-nose system: (a) architecture and (b) prototype developed

Table 1. List of the MOS sensors in the device

Sensor	Target odor	Secondary odors
S1	Combustible gas	H ₂ , LPG, CH ₄ , CO, alcohol, and propane
S2	Alcohol	CO and H ₂
S3	Methane	Propane and butane
S4	Carbon monoxide	H ₂ , LPG, and CH ₄
S5	Hydrogen	CO
S6	Air quality	NH ₃ , NO _x , alcohol, benzene, smoke, and CO ₂
S7	Organic gases	acetone, alcohol, toluene, and hydrogen

The output signal from each sensor i is converted into a sinusoid $g(t)$ with variable frequency proportional to the odor concentration present at the time t , that is (1):

$$g_i(t) = \sin [2\pi(f_0 + \Delta_i(t))t] \quad (1)$$

where f_0 is the carrier frequency of the signal ($f_0=1$ Hz) and $\Delta_i(t) = 0.1R$ is a variable term with R being a resistive proportionality constant that relates the odor concentration found in the sensor i at a given time t .

As example, Figure 2 shows the responses $g_i(t)$ of all seven sensors to butane. According to (1), the response will be a sinusoid of 1 Hz with amplitude 1 that increases its frequency according to the sensor's

sensitivity to the odor. Note that sensor S1 is practically insensitive to butane while S3 is the sensor that exhibits the highest sensitivity to this odor.

Figure 2. The sensors' response to butane

2.2. Filter diagonalization method

This research explores the use of the FDM to transform the signals obtained from the set of sensors into the frequency domain. We have previously demonstrated in [16] that FDM outperforms Fourier algorithms by providing more accurate spectra especially when using datasets with a limited number of samples. The application of FDM in e-noses represents a novel contribution, as this method has traditionally been used in quantum mechanics [17], magnetic resonance machines [18], and leak detection in pipelines [19].

FDM is a two-step technique that extracts the most important features from a signal. In the first step, an autocorrelation matrix constructed from the signal is diagonalized. This process involves finding a transformation matrix that converts the autocorrelation matrix into a diagonal matrix containing eigenvalues, each representing a frequency component of the signal. In the second step, a filter is applied to the eigenvalues of the diagonal matrix to retain only those that represent the most significant harmonics of the signal.

Let us address the method by considering a complex signal $c_n=c(n\tau)$ where $n\tau$ are equidistant-time values with $n=0, 1, \dots, N-1$. The FDM represents signal c_n as a sum of damped sinusoids, as shown in (2):

$$c_n = \sum_{k=1}^K d_k e^{-jn\tau\omega_k} \tag{2}$$

where d_k are the corresponding amplitudes and $\omega_k = 2\pi f_k - j\gamma_k$ are the complex frequencies of the signal with γ_k being the harmonic decay. To solve (1), the FDM uses the Hamiltonian operator $\hat{\Omega}$ to construct a correlation function with complex eigenvalues $\{\omega_k\}$, thus yielding (3):

$$c_n = (\Phi_0 | e^{-jn\tau\hat{\Omega}} \Phi_0) \tag{3}$$

The problem can be simplified to the diagonalization of the Hamiltonian operator $\hat{\Omega}$ or, as discussed in [20], to the evolution operator $\hat{U} = e^{-j\tau\hat{\Omega}}$. Briefly, a symmetric internal product operator defined by $(a|b)=(b|a)$ without the conjugate complex is considered, where Φ_0 is the initial state. Given that an orthonormal eigenvector set Y_k is used to perform the diagonalization of \hat{U} as shown in (4):

$$\hat{U} = \sum_k u_k |Y_k\rangle\langle Y_k| = \sum_k e^{-j\omega_k\tau} |Y_k\rangle\langle Y_k| \tag{4}$$

and replacing (4) in (3), it yields (5):

$$d_k = (\Phi_0 | Y_k)\langle Y_k | \psi_0) = (Y_k | \Phi_0)^2 \tag{5}$$

The resulting eigenvalues determine the harmonics' position and width while the eigenvectors define their amplitudes and phases. Assuming a set created from the Krylov vectors, generated by the evolution operator $\Phi_n = \hat{U}^n \Phi_0 = e^{-jn\tau\hat{\Omega}} \Phi_0$ and according to (5), it yields:

$$(\Phi_n | \hat{U} \Phi_m) = (\Phi_n | \Phi_{m+1}) = c_{m+n+1} \quad (6)$$

Given that the set is non-orthonormal, the overlapping matrix can be calculated according to (7):

$$(\Phi_n | \Phi_m) = (\hat{U}^n \Phi_0 | \hat{U}^m \Phi_0) = (\Phi_0 | \hat{U}^{m+n} \Phi_0) = c_{m+n+1} \quad (7)$$

Notation U^0 can then be used, being this the overlapping matrix representation of dimensions $M+1 \times M+1$. Similarly, U^1 can be used for \hat{U} . To reformulate (2), it is then necessary to solve the generalized eigenvalues problem as shown in (8):

$$U^1 B_k = u_k U^0 B_k \quad (8)$$

where $u_k = e^{-jn\omega_k\tau}$ contains the lines of the spectrum and its corresponding widths. Eigenvectors B_k contain both amplitudes and phases.

To analyze the sensors' data with FDM, let us consider the sensors' readings as the signals c_n . Figure 3 shows the flowchart detailing the algorithm implementation.

Figure 3. Six-step algorithm for the FDM implementation in the e-nose

- After acquisition, signals c_n are loaded, N is their number of samples, and f_s is their sampling frequency. Finally, the frequency interval $[f_{min} f_{max}]$ in which the spectral analysis will be performed is selected.
- The grid step size is created with angular frequency values $2\pi f_{min} < \varphi_j < 2\pi f_{max}$ with $j=0, 1, 2, \dots, K_{win}$ and $K_{win} = \frac{N(f_{max}-f_{min})}{2\tau}$.
- Three symmetric complex matrices $U^{(p)}$ of dimensions $K_{win} \times K_{win}$, with $p=0, 1, 2$ are determined. In (9) is used to calculate the elements located in the diagonal:

$$U^{(p)}(\varphi, \varphi') = \sum_{n=0}^{2M} (M+1 - |m-n|) e^{jn\varphi} \quad (9)$$

- The generalized eigenvalues problem is solved with (8) and the QZ algorithm [21].
- The complex amplitudes d_k are selected using (10):

$$d_k^{1/2} = \sum_{j=1}^{K_{win}} \mathbf{B}_{jk} \sum_{n=0}^M c_n e^{jn\varphi_j} \quad (10)$$

- Resulting values ω_k and d_k are finally used to estimate the FDM spectrum $C(F)$ according to (11):

$$C(F) = - \sum_k \text{Im} \left\{ \frac{d_k}{2\pi F - \omega_k} \right\} \quad (11)$$

2.3. Random forest

RF is a supervised learning model that combines multiple decision trees into a single model to reach a more accurate and stable prediction [22]. This algorithm was chosen because it is commonly used in classification tasks and is especially useful on large and complex datasets [23]-[25], such as the ones produced by the e-nose sensors. The process of building an RF model for odor classification is the following:

- A subset of features from the FDM dataset is randomly selected.
- These attributes are used to construct a decision tree.

- c. Steps 1 and 2 are repeated several times to create a set of decision trees (a forest).
- d. Each tree in the forest predicts an individual output (a class). The output of the RF model is the class selected by most trees.

Figure 4 shows the simplified structure of the RF model used for odor classification.

Figure 4. RF model implemented for the e-nose

2.4. Experimentation

To assess the performance of the FDM-RF approach a set of 224 trials was randomly performed in the following scenarios: i) presence of acetone, ii) presence of alcohol, iii) presence of butane, and iv) no odor (clean air). To ensure a proper odor distribution around the sensors, the e-nose was placed inside a hermetic acrylic enclosure. Outside the setup, an air pump was deployed to transport the odor samples to the acrylic cabinet via a hose. The experiment starts with the cabinet closed isolating the e-nose from the outside. For the first 20 seconds, all seven sensors acquire data from the air present in the cabinet (clean air). The pump is turned on and starts to draw the sample odor into the cabinet. For the next 30 seconds, the pump will remain activated ensuring that the acrylic cabinet is filled with the sample odor. The pump is then turned off and for the next 130 seconds, the odor will remain in the cabinet allowing the sensors to react. The experiment is concluded by opening the acrylic box and allowing the sample to dissipate in the environment. The sensors' collected data is sent to the computer for off-line analysis and classification.

This experimental protocol was used to train the RF model. Once trained, it is possible to classify new samples. Each time a new sample is analyzed and classified; it is incorporated into the model thus gradually increasing its robustness.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Following the experimental protocol described in section 2.4, let us analyze the results obtained for acetone. Figure 5 shows the sensors' temporal responses to such odor. As described by (1), the most sensitive sensors will be those that exhibit the sinusoids with the highest frequencies once the acetone fills the acrylic cabinet ($t > 50$ s). This is the case for sensors S4 and S7.

The temporal signals are then processed by the algorithm detailed in Figure 3. Figure 6 shows the corresponding FDM spectra. Relevant features to discuss are: i) the green-dashed line in all seven spectra is the harmonic describing the 1 Hz carrier, ii) as the amplitude of the sinusoid signal is 1, the maximum value of $C(F)$ is 0.5, iii) the sooner a harmonic appears in the spectrum, the greater the slope of the temporal signal meaning a higher concentration of the target odor, and iv) a group of closely located harmonics means the sensor is highly sensitive to the target odor (e.g., S7). Each of the seven spectra can be considered a unique footprint for acetone and all together will integrate the FDM dataset to be analyzed by the RF classification model.

Figure 5. The sensors' response to acetone

Figure 6. The FDM-based spectra for the signals collected by the sensors

Figure 7 shows the confusion matrix summarizing the RF model prediction accuracy. The rows correspond to the true class while the columns indicate the predicted class. Values on the diagonal represent (top) the number of times the odor was presented to the e-nose and (bottom) the corresponding recognition rate. For example, acetone was presented 51 times and was always recognized (recognition rate: 100%). Alcohol was presented 49 times out of which 47 times it was correctly recognized (recognition rate: 95.9%). The overall recognition rate across the 224 trials is 96.4% which suggests that RF is an adequate model to classify FDM footprints of odors.

		Predicted class			
		acetone	air	alcohol	butane
True class	acetone	51 100%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%
	air	0 0.0%	69 100%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%
	alcohol	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	47 95.9%	2 4.1%
	butane	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	55 100%

Figure 7. Confusion matrix of the RF model for odor classification

4. CONCLUSION

This paper has presented a prototype of a low-cost, compact e-nose system designed to detect specific environmental odors that may pose risks to human health. The system consists of seven gas sensors, an electronic unit, and dedicated software for signal processing and classification. The signal processing stage is based on the FDM, a novel non-Fourier data processing algorithm that provides spectra containing the most relevant features of the temporal signals. By calculating the FDM-based spectra for each of the seven signals provided by the sensors, reliable footprints can be established for target odors. The classification stage employs a RF model to identify the odors in the e-nose's surroundings. Experimental results show that the RF model achieves a 96.4% classification accuracy. To the best of our knowledge, the combined use of FDM and RF is a novel contribution to odor detection and classification, offering a promising approach for e-nose systems. Future work will compare the classification accuracy of the RF model with other models, such as neural networks, k-nearest neighbors, and support vector machine.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This research is funded by the School of Engineering of Universidad Panamericana via a Ph.D. scholarship.

REFERENCES

- [1] R. Radi *et al.*, "Implementation of an electronic nose for classification of synthetic flavors," *Bulletin of Electrical Engineering and Informatics*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 1283–1290, 2021, doi: 10.11591/eei.v10i3.3018.
- [2] L. Capelli, S. Sironi, and R. D. Rosso, "Electronic noses for environmental monitoring applications," *Sensors (Switzerland)*, vol. 14, no. 11, pp. 19979–20007, 2014, doi: 10.3390/s141119979.
- [3] M. P. A. F. Kiki, S. A. R. M. Ahouandjinou, K. M. Assogba, and T. Sutikno, "Bibliometric analysis and survey on electronic nose used in agriculture," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 14, no. 2, pp. 1369–1381, 2024, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v14i2.pp1369-1381.
- [4] P. Rai and S. H. Saeed, "Detection of harmful gases present in the environment," *Indonesian Journal of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science (IJECS)*, vol. 30, no.1, pp. 70–80, 2023, doi: 10.11591/ijeecs.v30.i1.pp70-80.
- [5] S. O. Mishra and S. H. Saeed, "Optimization of electronic sensors for detecting pollution due to organic gases using PARAFAC," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 9, no. 5, pp. 3441–3449, 2019, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v9i5.pp3441-3449.
- [6] M. I. Mead *et al.*, "The use of electrochemical sensors for monitoring urban air quality in low-cost, high-density networks," *Atmospheric Environment*, vol. 70, pp. 186–203, 2013, doi: 10.1016/j.atmosenv.2012.11.060.

- [7] J. Goschnick, I. Koroncz, M. Frietsch, and I. Kiselev, "Water pollution recognition with the electronic nose KAMINA," *Sensors and Actuators B: Chemical*, vol. 106, no. 1, pp. 182-186, 2005, doi: 10.1016/j.snb.2004.05.055.
- [8] Y. Wang *et al.*, "Electronic nose application for detecting different odorants in source water: Possibility and scenario," *Environmental Research*, vol. 227, 115677, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.envres.2023.115677.
- [9] S. Deshmukh *et al.*, "Application of electronic nose for industrial odors and gaseous emissions measurement and monitoring—An overview," *Talanta*, vol. 144, pp. 329-340, 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.talanta.2015.06.050.
- [10] M. Reiser *et al.*, "Fugitive methane and odour emission characterization at a composting plant using remote sensing measurements," *Global NEST Journal*, vol. 20, no. 3, pp. 674-677, 2018, doi: 10.30955/gnj.002802.
- [11] B. J. Lotesoriere *et al.*, "Electronic nose for odor monitoring at a landfill fenceline: Training and validation of a model for real-time odor concentration measurement," *Heliyon*, vol. 10, no. 10, e31103, 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e31103.
- [12] J. Gebicki, T. Dymerski, and J. Namiesnik, "Monitoring of odour nuisance from landfill using electronic nose," *Chemical Engineering Transactions*, vol. 40, pp. 85-90, 2014, doi: 10.3303/CET1440015.
- [13] P. Kanakam, S. M. Hussain, and A. S. N. Chakravarthy, "Electronic noses: Forestalling fire disasters: A technique to prevent false fire alarms and fatal casualties," *2015 IEEE International Conference on Computational Intelligence and Computing Research (ICCIIC)*, Madurai, India, 2015, pp. 1-6, doi: 10.1109/ICCIIC.2015.7435629.
- [14] A. Anyfantis, A. Silis and S. Blionas, "A low cost, mobile e-nose system with an effective user interface for real time victim localization and hazard detection in USaR operations," *Measurement: Sensors*, vol. 16, 100049, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.measen.2021.100049.
- [15] R. Macías-Quijas, R. Velázquez, N. I. Giannoccaro, and A. Lay-Ekuakille, "A Novel Electronic Nose Instrument for the Detection of Volatile Hazardous Compounds: Preliminary Results," *2021 7th International Conference on Control, Instrumentation and Automation (ICCIA)*, Tabriz, Iran, 2021, pp. 1-5, doi: 10.1109/ICCIA52082.2021.9403595.
- [16] R. Macías-Quijas *et al.*, "Reliable e-nose for air toxicity monitoring by filter diagonalization method," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 1286-1298, 2022, doi:10.11591/ijece.v12i2.pp1286-1298.
- [17] M. R. Wall and D. Neuhauser, "Extraction, through filter-diagonalization, of general quantum eigenvalues or classical normal mode frequencies from a small number of residues or a short-time segment of a signal. I. Theory and application to a quantum-dynamics model," *The Journal of chemical physics*, vol. 102, no. 20, pp. 8011-8022, 1995, doi: 10.1063/1.468999.
- [18] B. Dai and C. D. Eads, "Efficient removal of unwanted signals in NMR spectra using the filter diagonalization method," *Magnetic Resonance in Chemistry*, vol. 48, no. 3, pp. 230-234, 2010, doi: 10.1002/mrc.2550
- [19] A. Lay-Ekuakille, G. Vendramin, and A. Trotta, "Robust spectral leak detection of complex pipelines using filter diagonalization method," *IEEE Sensors Journal*, vol. 9, no. 11, pp. 1605-1614, Nov. 2009, doi: 10.1109/JSEN.2009.2027410.
- [20] V. A. Mandelshtam, "FDM: The filter diagonalization method for data processing in NMR experiments," *Progress in Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Spectroscopy*, vol. 38, no. 2, pp. 159-196, Mar. 2001, doi: 10.1016/S0079-6565(00)00032-7.
- [21] D. J. Evans and W. S. Yousif, "The QZ algorithm for the calculation of the eigenvalues of a real matrix," *Parallel Algorithms and Applications*, vol. 4, no. 3-4, pp. 183-192, 1994, doi: 10.1080/10637199408915463.
- [22] L. Breiman, "Random Forests," *Machine Learning*, vol. 45, pp. 5-32, 2001, doi: 10.1023/A:1010933404324.
- [23] V. M. Álvarez-Pato *et al.*, "A multisensor data fusion approach for predicting consumer acceptance of food products," *Foods*, vol. 9, no. 6, p. 774, 2020, doi: 10.3390/foods9060774.
- [24] C. N. Sánchez, M. Rivera, and R. Velázquez, "Robust multiband image segmentation method based on user clues," *2017 IEEE 37th Central America and Panama Convention (CONCAPAN XXXVII)*, Managua, Nicaragua, 2017, pp. 1-6, doi: 10.1109/CONCAPAN.2017.8278462.
- [25] T. A. Assegie, R. Subhashni, N. K. Kumar, J. P. Manivannan, P. Duraisamy, and M. F. Engidaye "Random forest and support vector machine based hybrid liver disease detection," *Bulletin of Electrical Engineering and Informatics*, vol. 11, no. 3, p. 1650-1656, 2022, doi: 10.11591/eei.v11i3.3787.

BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Ricardo Macías-Quijas received the Engineering degree in Electronics and Digital Communication Systems from Universidad Autónoma de Aguascalientes (Mexico) in 2001 and the Master degree in Electrical Engineering (Telecommunications) from CINVESTAV (Mexico) in 2004. He is currently pursuing the Ph.D. degree in Engineering at Universidad Panamericana (Mexico). He teaches electronics, digital signal processing and communication systems at the School of Engineering of Universidad Panamericana. His research interests include advanced digital signal processing algorithms, electronics, and telecommunication systems. He can be contacted at email: rmacias@up.edu.mx.

Ramiro Velázquez is full professor at the School of Engineering of Universidad Panamericana (Mexico). He received the Engineering degree in Electronics from Universidad Bonaterra (Mexico) in 1999, the M.Sc. degree in Control Systems from INSA-Lyon (France) in 2000, and the Ph.D. in Robotics from Université Pierre et Marie Curie – Paris 6 (France) in 2006. He has been a visiting lecturer at Universidad del Magdalena (Santa Marta, Colombia), ASKSiM (Torun, Poland) and Universidad de La Salle (Bogota, Colombia). He has authored more than 200 journals and conferences papers. His main research interests are mechatronic systems, assistive technology, haptic and tactile devices, and human perception. He can be contacted at email: rvelazquez@up.edu.mx.

Carolina Del-Valle-Soto is a research professor and head of the computing academy at the School of Engineering of Universidad Panamericana (Guadalajara, Mexico). She holds a Ph.D. in Information and Communication Technologies and a Master degree in Electronic Engineering (Telecommunications) both from Tecnológico de Monterrey (Mexico). She has authored over 80 solid research pieces, prestigious conferences, and dissemination books. Her main research areas are wireless sensor networks, energy consumption studies, and security in wireless technologies, as well as robotics for healthcare. She can be contacted at email: cvalle@up.edu.mx.

Rafal Lizut received the M.Sc. in Civil Engineering from Technical University of Lublin (Poland), the Ph.D. in Philosophy from John Paul II University of Lublin, the PGD in Computer Science from Technical University of Lublin, and the Ph.D. Hab in Economy from Kharkiv Petro Vasylenko National Technical University of Agriculture (Ukraine). He is a Professor of IT in Poland, Nigeria, and Ukraine. He is chairman of the academy of scientific, academic excellence, and cultural exchange of Poland and expert at the Academy of European Careers in Poland. His main research areas are AI algorithms, swarm intelligence, and applications of AI. He can be contacted at email: rafal.lizut@kul.pl.

Paolo Visconti is an associate professor at the Department of Innovation Engineering of Salento University (Italy) in the field of electronic design, analog/digital sensing devices, IoT-based smart systems, and signal acquisition circuits. His main research topics include the design and testing of IoT-based electronic solutions for data acquisition and monitoring, electronic systems for automation and automotive, energy harvesting systems for sensor nodes and wearable applications, and new materials and advanced sensors for healthcare and biomedical applications. He coordinates a research group of young researchers in collaboration with foreign universities and research centers. He is the author of more than 200 research-indexed articles. He can be contacted at email: paolo.visconti@unisalento.it.

Aimé Lay-Ekuakille received the M.D. degree in Electronic Engineering from the University of Bari (Italy), in 1988, a second M.D. degree in Clinical Engineering from the University of L'Aquila (Italy), in 2002, and a Ph.D. in Electronic Engineering from the Polytechnic of Bari in 2001. Since 2000, he has been with the Department of Innovation Engineering, University of Salento (Italy). He is the Director of the Instrumentation and Measurement Lab. He is a Senior Member of IEEE. His main areas of research are instrumentation and measurements for biomedical, environmental and industrial applications, sensors and sensing systems, and AI for instrumentation and measurement. He has authored more than 340 indexed papers and 5 books. He can be contacted at email: aime.lay.ekuakille@unisalento.it.